

**THE CHALLENGES FACING DOMESTIC WORKERS; A CASE STUDY OF PHASE 2-
GABORONE.**

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CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1 OVERVIEW

Domestic workers face a wide range of grave abuses and labor exploitation, including physical and sexual abuse, forced confinement, non payment of wages, denial of food and health care and excessive working hours with no rest days. According to Hosmer and Mitter (1994) estimating the prevalence of abuse is difficult given the lack of reporting mechanisms, the lack of legal protections and restrictions on the freedom of domestic workers movement. However, the International Labor Organization (<http://www.ilo.reports/domesticworkers.org>) states that there are many indications that abuses are widespread. For example, in Saudi Arabia, the embassies of Indonesia, Sri Lanka and Phillipines handle thousands of complaints every year. In January 2004, for example, Sri Lankan embassy estimated that it was receiving about 150 domestic workers each month that had fled abusive employers. Moreover, according to information provided by embassies in Singapore, at least 147 domestic workers have fallen to their deaths from tall buildings since 1998 due to hazardous workplace conditions or suicide.

Anderson (2000) asserts that domestic workers in Europe are from a wide range of class background, including the landless and poor families. She claims that the treatment of domestic worker and the demand for them in the first place is symptomatic of fundamental contradictions and tensions with capitalism which is both racist and patriarchal. According to Whyte (1991), in Donald and Mogwe (1997), domestic workers in South Africa have been mistreated as invisible workers and non persons whose work and very presence are taken for granted.

Cock (1989), in her research, entitled 'Maids and Madams; Domestic Workers under Apartheid', clearly outlined the conditions of domestic workers which she claimed subjected them to conditions of ultra-exploitation, for example, being denied a negotiated wage, reasonable working hours, and family and social life. According to Motlhale (1995), domestic workers in Botswana are exploited in that they do not receive any paid leave, are not paid for overtime, they have no minimum wages and that their

payment varies according to what the employer can offer. They are also subjected to what the employer can offer and long hours of over time which are not paid for. That is, they do not have clear job description hence they are tasked to any duty in the household or even at the employer's fields and cattle post.

1.2 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The Botswana for Human Rights (1996) notes that the situations and circumstances of domestic workers in Botswana, including house helpers, child minders and other such workers are bad, Issues raised by the Centre have been the question of bargaining power, the definition and validation of their employment, and the limitations and lack of effective protection by the law or local legislation. Therefore, this study aims at investigating the working and living conditions of domestic workers as well as associated challenges and measures that can improve their welfare. The working and living conditions include, among others, the nature of relationship that exist between domestic workers and their employers. The challenges and measures for improvement takes into account factors such as social relationships with their families and partners as well as economic factors such as the monthly wages, overtime with no pay and work risks which are not entitled to compensation.

1.3 OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

The study on domestic workers seeks to:

- ❖ Investigate the working and living conditions of domestic workers.
- ❖ Examine the problems which domestic workers encounter in their work.
- ❖ Describe the relationship between domestic workers and their employers.
- ❖ Identify measures to improve the welfare of domestic workers.

1.4 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- ❖ What are the working and living conditions of domestic workers?
- ❖ What are the actual problems that domestic workers encounter in their work?
- ❖ What is the nature of the relationship between domestic workers and their employers?
- ❖ What measures are necessary to improve the welfare of domestic workers?

1.5 SIGNIFICANCE OF STUDY

This study is about the challenges facing domestic workers. These include their conditions of work and the implication of economic factors such as low to nil monthly wages of the workers' welfare. Women form a larger proportion of the population in the society and Tswana values and norms associate women to domestic work. Therefore, the findings of this study may influence policy makers, women empowerment and advocacy organisations in Botswana, and law makers or government to work towards improving the welfare of domestic workers. Botswana government may take action to establish legislation covering domestic workers so as to encourage self reliance, which is one of the Pillars of Botswana's vision 2016.

Practitioners such as social workers may get an insight into the issues that affect domestic workers and as such they may come up with ways or approaches to adopt when dealing with them. Policy makers as mentioned may take informed decisions as per the findings of the study on the economic and social conditions of domestic workers. Individuals may also get exposure and perhaps help to promote domestic work through forming domestic workers association. The study also adds to the search for appropriate measures to improve the welfare of domestic workers.

1.6 RESEARCH IMPLICATION

Looking at the fact that not much has been done on domestic workers' issues in Botswana, findings of this study will add to the scanty literature on domestic workers in Botswana. The findings may influence future research on domestic workers in the labour market as well as helping to identify the areas that need to be explored or researched in assisting domestic workers.

1.7 DEFINITION OF TERMS

Domestic Work: According to Anderson (2000), domestic work is work such as domestic chores, performed by a person in another home for remuneration. Domestic chores include laundry, ironing, cooking, cleaning, and serving in an exchange for a wage. She maintains that feminists have tended to regard domestic work as the great leveler, a common burden imposed on women by patriarchy and lazy husbands. Busia (1989) in Donald and Mogwe (1997:23) suggests that it was colonialism that brought with it the notion of domestic as a form of paid labour although she qualifies this by saying that even today, the name domestic servant or worker within the African Context is a misnomer and that, "the duties they perform without any corresponding rights, make slaves in all but name".

Domestic worker: The Botswana Centre for Human Rights (1995) describes domestic work as often seen both by employees and employers as a private issue rather than a labour issue. A domestic worker is a person whose full time job is to work in a household for someone else. Similarly Letsie-Taole (1992) refers to a domestic worker as a woman and suggests that this arises out of the fact that an overwhelming number of domestic workers are universally women.

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 INTRODUCTION

In the micro politics of the home as a work place, the key struggles are over the control of the labour process, outputs and conditions and terms on which the work is done. Therefore, domestic work as a service that exists across the global village is remarkably essential hence its persistence in most countries. This text serves to review the literature pertaining to the challenges, living and working conditions as well as the nature of relationship between domestic workers and their employers. The focus is also on the measures to improve the welfare of domestic workers.

According to Anderson (2000), domestic work is vital and sustaining. Pennington and Westover (1989) assert that domestic work is often attached to loneliness, isolation, over work and very little time though it is considered more respectable than factory or agricultural work as it is a home in the context of a family type situation.

2.2 DOMESTIC WORKER AS A WOMAN

Pennington and Westover (1989) state that in the mid nineteenth century, domestic service was, in general, the only employment open to single women. Similarly, Letsie-Taole (1992) acknowledges that men have, in different points in history, worked as domestic workers. However, she asserts that activities comprising domestic work such as cleaning, cooking, laundry and child care have almost universally been associated with women and care performed within the home. In agreement with her, Cock (1981) and Davis (1983) in Letsie-Taole (1992) argue that the personal service aspect of domestic work also conforms to the universal view of women and wives rendering personal service to their families and husbands. Similarly, Donald and Mogwe (1997) contend that in the African context, the class dimension is discussed from a historical perspective of colonization and neo colonisation under the missionary education for domesticity. For instance, Makati (1986) in her study, found out that domestic workers in Gaborone have undefined working conditions as an effect of this differential 'proletarianisation' of African men and women. However, she states that knowledge of working conditions is vital because in all circumstances, all wage labor came to be seen

as a wage labor for men. Botswana, therefore, as a democratic country, has to allow everyone to have the right to know his or her working conditions. Segregation measures rendered domestic work the only viable alternative for women.

Modisa (1980) in Makati (1986) argue that the modern woman or wife is no more a house wife. Though segregation rendered domestic work as the only alternative for women, house wifery tasks are carried out by the distinguished house wife called a domestic worker, a female. The modern husbands spends hours working, reading papers and chatting with friends at meeting places and hence their duties such as washing cars, cutting lawn and general gardening are assigned to a paid home care takers. She mentioned that domestic workers are one of the most productive economic factors in the economy. They may not contribute directly to the economy but their contribution is quite significant. Rollins (1985) and Romeo (1992) in Mendez (1998) similarly assert than an ideology of domestic workers as being just like one of the family 'has been well documented in the context of private employment situations, masking poor work conditions, low pay and long working hours. Within this ideology, the worker replaces the house wife whose work is constructed as labour of love' (<http://www.jstor.org>).

2.3 THE NATURE OF DOMESTIC WORK

The nature of domestic work centers around home environment as workplace for domestic workers, and the home owners as the employers or supervisors. The actors monitor their mutual interaction un an uneasy labor relationship whose ambiguous, personalized nature is mediated by the process of cooperation and conflict (Giddens (1983) in Hansen (1990).

2.3.1 WORKING AND LIVING CONDITIONS OF DOMESTIC WORKERS

According to Lenaghan (1995) domestic work in Botswana is undervalued, invisible and underpaid. People doing this job do not have adequate legal protection. They face many problems including poor working conditions, unregulated working hours and inadequate pay. She further adds that domestic workers are often employed without any clear explanation by the employer thus making domestic workers vulnerable to exploitation and bad treatment. Donald and Mogwe (1997) note that it is partly due to the isolated and isolating nature of the work which makes it difficult for them to engage effectively in collective bargaining power for fair working conditions.

Domestic workers are one of the weakest and most vulnerable section of the labor force in Botswana. Their work hours are long, their pay is low and their conditions of work are often poor. To make matters worse, there is little legislation to protect them. They are not adequately covered by the Employment Act of 1984 and the isolated nature of their work makes it hard for them to organize to press for change. For most poor women, domestic work is the only source of income. Low levels of education and training mean that they have few alternatives (Ditshwanelo, (1997). In assertion to this, Makati (1986) affirms that domestic workers in Gaborone have undefined working conditions including their holiday entitlement as well as hours of work.

Domestic workers who have little education are better off than those who have never been to school because those who have been to school are working in high class and medium strata where their employers are expatriates, in most cases. Some stay with their employers, hence making them to work day and night. Those in medium and high cost houses are better than those in low cost houses because they have access to the servant's quarters.

Whyte (1991) in Donald and Mogwe (1997) maintains that the relationship with their employers, exempted by lack of employment contracts and legally enforceable statutory protection, make them more akin to informal sector workers. However, Mogwe and Donald (1997) allude that in South Africa, as from 1994, basic working conditions were

granted to domestic workers under the Basic Conditions of Employment Act (BCEA, No3 1983, Amended) which covered every aspect of formal sector.

In addition Pape (September 1993) states that at the independence of Zimbabwe there were about 108 000 domestic workers and by nearly any measure, they occupied the lowest position amongst the urban working class. Unlike workers in industry, domestic workers were not covered by any labor legislation and the only law governing their work conditions was the Masters and Servants Act of 1903. This Act stated that it is a criminal offence for a 'servant' to refuse to perform a reasonable order of the; master'. However, the government of Zimbabwe took steps to improve the conditions of domestic workers and those include the creation of legalized system of labour relations and support the formation of domestic workers union. Therefore, the domestic workers in Zimbabwe obtained their work place rights such as the right to join trade unions and entitlement to a minimum wage.

Rollins (1985) states that research in Boston, Massachusetts, found that domestic work was generally a low prestige and low reward occupation in to which workers are forced by lack of economic and employment alternatives. Rollins (1985) further maintains that domestic work has been the largest source of employment for women in the 19th century but in the period following world war one, white women with skills and education moved into wage labor and clerical positions. Black women who comprised 28.8% of the domestic sector before the war, increased to be 45.8% of the sector by 1920. Domestic work provided the easiest and fastest route into the city wage labor. She notes that the exploitation of domestic workers represents the contradiction between the domestic worker and her employer who cherishes the domestic workers surrogate parenthood to her children while domestic workers' children are left unattended. While researchers agree that the overwhelming majority of domestic workers are immigrants and African American women, Romeo (1992) postulate that the historical account reveals that domestic work became low status and demeaning as a result of dominating presence of immigrants and nonwhites. On the contrary, Martin and Segrave (1985) argue that domestic work was always viewed as low status and undesirable. They claim

that white domestic workers were able to use domestic work as a bridging occupation, while immigrants and native born blacks remain in this 'occupational ghetto' due to lack of alternatives.

Anderson (2000) alludes that domestic workers in Europe classify their employment, not as type of work done but whether it is live in or out. Live in is often, though by no means of always, associated with caring for children, the elderly and those with disability. Live out refers to working for several employers, and is generally task oriented, for instance, laundry making and cleaning. While performance of some form of domestic labour is necessary to ensure the daily and generational reproduction of individuals within the household, it is labor performed irrespective of whether or not those individuals sell their labor power on the market. Briefly, domestic work is not exchanged directly against variable capital. It is not production of commodities, it is not allocated according to the law value and it does not constitute a source of surplus value for the capitalist. It is not productive in the Marxist sense. Thus a domestic worker is privatized and geared for private consumption, with low use value. It is therefore unproductive and in that sense neither the housewife nor domestic worker can be seen as exploited by capitalists in relation to their performance of domestic work (Gaitskell et al 1984 in Letsie-Taole 1990).

2.3.2 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE WORKER AND EMPLOYER

Domestic workers are in isolated, individualized employment relationships, and subjected to highly unequal power relations. As such they are amongst the workers most in need of strong interventions which protect their rights and which go some way towards equalizing the power relationship. The market for domestic labor has always been the very model of a so called "flexible labor market"-wage rates at the discretion of individual employers, limited worker organization, great flexibility (both upwards and downwards) in the number of days and hours worked, task flexibility, and no barriers to discretionary firing of workers. With a similar claim, Lenaghan (1995) argues that since domestic workers work as single workers in a home environment, it has been difficult

for employers to recognise them as having the same rights as other workers. Most of the workers walk away from home for regular set of hours and payment. The domestic worker however is seen as property rates than as a worker because she is often denied her rights.

Hansen (May 1990) asserts that the difficulties servants and employers in Zambia encounter in their relationship are by no means unique. Studies such as *Still Serving the Tea* by Pape (1980) show that regardless of time and place, the service tends to involve a problematic relationship. Its vexing nature has been attributed to the personalized character of the labour process in the household as contrasted with the more contractual, organisational relationship of factory and office workers to their employers. The troublesome relationship of inequality between servants and employers has been taken to epitomize domination and its unhappy companion, subordination. The social relations are influenced by the general view that domestic work is inferior, servile and low in status (<http://www.jstorjournal.org>). Rollins (1985), in Letsie-Taole (1992), adds that domestic work is grounded in stratification. It is always low in the class hierarchy, always composed of people considered inferior by virtue of their unfree status, their gender, geographic origins, and lower background. This makes the occupation universally despised and those involved in it, universally de-humanised.

Hondagneu-Sotela (February 1994) affirms that the mistress- servant relationship is a private labour arrangements. This is because it takes place within private households between fairly isolated individuals. Today labour process in domestic service turns on the shared need (though for different reasons) for security of employ and servants: the one for household comfort and protection of material property, the other for economic survival. A new kind of personalised dependency relationship has emerged. It is a dependency relationship in which neither party lines up to the standard or the other's expectation. Employers see it as a blessing in disguise, while servants generally term their employers as unreliable (<http://www.jstorjournal.org>).

2.3.3 PROBLEMS FACING DOMESTIC WORKERS

Contemporary employers complain that servants are inefficient, lazy and lack any sense of foresight. Servants are also seen as unreliable, dishonest, irresponsible, squander their money, and disappear without notice. Again they see servants as having different or strange cultural ideas and relations with spouses, dependents, and in laws; work habits; and notions of time and duty (Hansen, May 1990 in <http://www.jstor.org>). However, Leon (1986) in Letsie-Taole (1992) argues that the relationship between the domestic worker and her employer cannot be described in purely economic terms. She also underscores the importance of the social context in which this labour relation is clouded.

Leon (1986) found that wages of workers were not set in place with economic factors. Subjection factors such as good treatment as perceived by the employers, played important part. Another aspects of labour relation is that the employee lives in the workplace "but she is confined to a physical space different from that of the family, rendering explicitly the class difference. This arrangement also means that the worker is constantly available and that the employers exert a strong influence on her social and sexual relationships. Consequently, her entire life is a function of labour relation. The large unregulated work hours, and with arbitrary wages combine with the above factors to render the worker helpless and powerless.

A domestic worker is also faced with the physical and emotional dislocation of her culture and social relationships. She is forced to transfer her emotional dependence to the employer's home. Hansen (1990) asserts that in this relationship they are both vulnerable, although the servant is more so than the employer. The employer controls more economic means and has more power than the servant. The government's inability to enforce its labour laws sends but one message to the employers: do as you want. The interaction between issues of class, race and gender intersect powerfully in domestic service. The relationship between the servant and employer is based on an exchange of labour power in return of wage. However, the wage to be allocated to the worker is based on the discretion of the employer who sometimes pays the worker in the form of clothing. For example, the Human Rights Watch (2006) (in

<http://www.hrw.org/reports>) states that migrant domestic workers in the Middle East and Asia are extremely vulnerable to withholding and non payment of salary, as well as arbitrary and illegal deductions from their salaries.

According to the Human Rights Watch (2006), domestic workers are almost always grossly underpaid for the long hours they are required to work. Denied by law the right to a minimum wage and overtime pay in most countries, domestic workers usually earn well below service sector minimum wages and prevailing wages for comparable work typically performed by men, for example gardening and driving. Child domestic workers, and women and girls who have traveled abroad to find work, are at a particular disadvantage because of their relative inability to negotiate a decent wage. Employers, labor agents, and even government authorities often justify low wages by claiming that women and girls earn more than they would at home, and that expenses for food and lodging must be factored in to arrive at the real wage. However, official guidelines for calculating deductions and minimum quality standards for food and accommodation are usually lacking. In these conditions, the provision of (often inadequate) food and lodging is used as an excuse for labor exploitation.

2.3.4 MEASURES TO IMPROVE THE WELFARE OF DOMESTIC WORKERS

Domestic workers' powerlessness or identification of the occupation with housework is seen as non work calls for the intervention of the state to enforce the workplace rights of domestic workers as well as identify domestic work as in informal sector of employment. Domestic workers in Southern Africa, particularly in South Africa and Zimbabwe obtained statutory obligation on working hours and overtime as well as their work covered on a contractual basis similar to workers in the formal sectors (Whyte, 1991). Donald and Mogwe (1997) add that the government of Botswana needs to demonstrate political will to ensure that domestic work is valued and some ways in which this could be done are:

- ❖ To provide domestic work with a financial allocation in the National Development Plans and the national budget, for example, by including vocational training for domestic workers under the educational sector.

- ❖ To include domestic work in policy formulation thereby formally recognizing such work.
- ❖ Finally, to provide protective legislation for both the employer and the worker such that they have a mandatory requirement that the employers enter into a written contracts with their employees. These contracts should detail the nature of work, salary, public holidays, and benefits and there should be a mandatory monitoring by both the government and non governmental organization working in this field.

2.4 CONCLUSION

Domestic workers suffer indignities in most countries. In spite of this, domestic work is one of the largest sources of employment. This, however, impacts negatively on the economy of the country as many people live under the poverty datum line. However measures to improve the welfare of domestic workers are scarce in as far as Botswana is concerned. For example, domestic workers who suffer injuries on the job or work-related illnesses often have no means to seek compensation or redress for the harm suffered. Ill or sick domestic workers can only trust, often in vain, in the kindness of their employers. Therefore, domestic workers particularly in Botswana need the implementation of measures to improve their socio economic welfare such as validation of domestic work, overtime payment, leave days and off entitlement.

2.5 THEORITICAL FRAME WORK

This paper utilizes the theory of human motivation. The theory have been used to interpret and analyse the findings on the working and living conditions of domestic workers, the problems they encounter in their work as well as their relationship with their employers.

2.6 THEORY OF HUMAN MOTIVATION

The originator of this theory is Abraham Maslow (1908-1970). Maslow was first attracted to behaviorism and carried out studies in sexuality and dominance. He was first

influenced by psychoanalysis and dominance. He was influenced by psychoanalysis but became critical of its theory of motivation and developed his own. Maslow believed that behaviourists were overlooking what really matters to people, that is, their uniquely human hopes and aspirations. He argued that all human beings strive to achieve full potential in life. In order to achieve this, certain needs have to be satisfied (Atkinson, Smith and Bem, 1990).

Therefore, Maslow proposed a hierarchy of needs comprising five categories. According to Atkinson et al (1990), needs that are low in the hierarchy must at least be partially satisfied before needs that are higher in the hierarchy become important source of motivation. The five categories of needs from the low to high in the hierarchy are as follows:

Physiological needs: are the first to be satisfied. These are the basic needs which influence other needs such as self-actualization, esteem, belonging and safety needs. That is, an individual may first consider satisfying hunger, thirst and other bodily material necessities. These are shelter, water, food, health and sexual needs. These needs are more of survival than luxurious living.

Safety needs: These are the need to feel secure and safe and they can also be described as needs to secure protection, or feel out danger, chaos and anxiety. In this case, an individual may hire a security company for her house, may join medical aid as well as adopting measure such as indulging in sexual relationship with an employer so as to prevent any issues of being retrenched or even fired from work.

Belonginess and love needs: The need to affiliate with others, be competent and gain approval and recognition. This need may explain why people would like to be affiliated to certain church denominations, societies, as well getting involved in love relationships and some other forms of friendships.

Esteem needs: The need to achieve, be competent and gain approval and recognition. Achievement brings about motivation in that an individual eventually attain a sense of ownership in whatever the initiative taken. This sense of ownership influences people to

approve and recognise others. Consequently, a positive self concept is obtained if one's esteem needs are satisfied.

Self actualization: Maslow believed that the most highly evolved need in the hierarchy is self actualisation. This involves fulfillment of one's potential through creative productivity and self expression. It may be described as the best one can aspire and eventually become. This is all about what one desires to be without putting in place the judgment of other people. Personal growth is most key in this type of need.

2.7 APPLICATION OF THEORY TO THE DOMESTIC WORKERS STUDY

Looking at the theory of motivation, the need to satisfy physiological necessities maybe a propelling reason for domestic workers endurance or long stay in working environment where they are exploited. Usually, they do not receive any paid leave, are not paid for overtime, have no minimum wages, and are paid according to what the employer can offer. Failure to endure or adhere to these conditions may make a domestic worker lose her job thus making it difficult to satisfy basic needs. Therefore, the findings of this study are likely show that domestic workers continue to be exploited in such conditions in order to satisfy their basic needs.

The need to feel secure and safe may also be a reason for domestic workers acceptance of living their homes and stay in servant's quarters within their employers premises. Failure or disagreement to stay within the employer's premises may mean that the domestic worker may knock off late and travel to their homes at night. Also, it may meant the worker may not have accommodation in a particular place. Therefore, the findings are of this study are show that the domestic workers accept to stay within the yards or premises of their employers in order to feel safe , protected and away from danger or they may not have any proper accommodation. The need to affiliate with others, may also contribute to domestic workers acceptance or indulgence in love relationships with their employers to satisfy the need for affection, love and belonging.

Finally the need to achieve and gain recognition or approval may be a compelling reason for domestic workers to endure the abusive language that the employers and their siblings use towards them.

CHAPTER THREE: METHODOLOGY

3.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter covers the purpose of the study, methodology, sampling, data collection methods and time dimension.

3.2 PURPOSE OF STUDY

This study is descriptive, explanatory and exploratory in nature. According to Babbie and Mouton (2001), social research serves many purposes and the most common and useful purposes are exploration, description and explanation. The descriptive phase of this study will describe the relationship between domestic workers and their employers as well as the problems that domestic workers face in their work. Explanatory purpose of this research focuses on investigating the working and living conditions of domestic workers. The exploratory purpose will identify measures to improve the welfare of domestic workers. This is because most of the domestic workers are vulnerable to poverty, low payments and their rights are mostly violated in as far as leaves, holidays and overtime are concerned. Therefore, this exploratory purpose of the study will satisfy the curiosity and understanding of the researcher as well as adding the new insights on how to improve the welfare of domestic workers to the few existing literature of the same field.

3.3 TIME DIMENSION

This study is cross sectional in nature because the time frame for carrying out research is already determined by the department of social work. Babbie and Mouton (2001) assert that exploratory and descriptive studies are often cross sectional. Therefore, this study is a triangulatory-cross sectional study because it tries to generate insight into the challenges facing domestic workers. This study is triangulatory cross sectional in that it adopts descriptive, explanatory and exploratory purposes or designs within the specific time dimension that has already been determined. Data will be collected at one point in time only.

3.4 METHODOLOGY

The qualitative research method was used as to capture data on the challenges and experiences of domestic workers. Qualitative research method is a good fit method because it allow for the use of an interview guide to collect information. Moreover, qualitative method enables the researcher to observe social life in its natural habitat: to go where the action is and watch it, to produce a richer understanding of many social phenomena that can be achieved through other observational methods, provided that the researcher observes in a deliberate, well planned and active way(Babbie, 2004:281).

This method is also preferred because it allows the researcher to probe and clarify questions in a way that respondents would understand. Moreover, qualitative method allows the researcher to be the primary instrument for data collection and analysis. (Blalock and Blalock, 1982). This method will then provide an indepth understanding of domestic workers working and living conditions. The method will also help in finding out from domestic workers and policy makers the measures that can be taken to improve the welfare of domestic workers.

3.5 SAMPLING

Sampling is the process of selecting observations. Babbie (2004) states that there are two types of sampling, namely, probability sampling and non probability sampling. Sampling occurs when the researcher selects a sample based on his or her knowledge of the population, its elements or the nature of the research study.

3.6 SAMPLE SIZE

Qualitative research is often aimed at indepth and holistic understanding of a few cases rather than a general understanding of many cases. Therefore the sampling size is usually small (May, 2001). There is no stipulated statistical record for domestic workers in Phase 2. According to the department of Surveys and Mapping (1996), there are 2507 plots in phase 2 and within this number, there are undeveloped plots, schools,

churches and unoccupied houses as well as occupied houses. Since it is not a guarantee that all the houses which have been occupied have domestic workers, the researcher would like to assume the size of the sample. The researcher selected thirty respondents consisting of twenty domestic workers, seven domestic workers' employers, three stake holders who normally work on issues and disputes of domestic workers as well as their rights. These include a paralegal officer from the center for human rights, dispute officer and a social welfare officer from ministry of labor and home affairs. Since this study is qualitative, the sample size is usually small, ranging from 25-30 respondents. Therefore, the sample size selection remains justifiable on the basis of the time limit for data collection as well as the monetary resources to be used in the field.

3.7 STUDY SITE

This study has been carried out in Phase 2, Gaborone. Phase 2 is characterised by different houses which are owned by Botswana Housing Corporation (BHC), Self Help Housing Agency (SHHA), individual owners as well as BHC houses which have been hired by the government for her employees. Within Phase two, there are schools and churches. Housing structures in this area range from high cost, medium cost and low cost thus accommodating different lifestyles in the area.

3.8 STUDY POPULATION AND UNIT OF ANALYSIS

The study population is all domestic workers working in phase 2 households. The unit of analysis or elements include domestic workers, their employers, policy makers and the Botswana Center for Human Rights paralegal officers.

3.9 SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

Qualitative and quantitative research approach the sampling process differently. This study, therefore, will utilize snowball sampling as a non probability sampling technique. Snowball sampling is a method of selecting cases in a network. That is, it begins with one or few people and widens out on the basis of the links to the initial cases (Neuman 2004). The researcher will then select the sample by approaching three domestic workers who will eventually link her with other domestic workers in Phase 2. Snowball sampling was used in selecting the domestic workers' employers. In selecting the key informants such as labor and paralegal officers, the researcher chose those who work with issues affecting domestic workers in their respective offices.

4.0 DATA COLLECTION METHOD

4.1 FACE TO FACE INTERVIEW

This data collection method is where the interviewer asks the respondents' questions in a face to face manner (Babbie 2004). The researcher had a personal contact with the respondents so that they express their views in a supported environment as the interviewer will clearly explain the questions administered. This face to face interview was administered to domestic workers, their employers some professionals such as labor officers and paralegal officers. Therefore, different interview guides were used. Moreover, this method enabled domestic workers to freely share their challenges without being intimidated by the presence of either their employers or other domestic workers. Problematic working relationships were also be covered during the interviews with the respondents. Domestic workers' employers were able to share their opinions concerning domestic work as well as the problems they encounter in their employer-employee relationships. Moreover, the stated professionals were able to articulate measures to improve the welfare of domestic workers as well as the problems they usually deal with in relation to domestic work.

4.2 DATA ANALYSIS PLAN

Qualitative process involves the non numerical assessment of observation, content analysis and in depth interviews (Babbie, 2004). According to Kerlinger (1973:134), data analysis is "recognising of data to obtain answers, accompanied by a closely related

procedure, interpretation which means to explain or find meaning". This study uses Huberman and Miles (Huberman, 1994) data analysis for research to analyse the data that has been collected from interviewing the respondents. According to Miles and Huberman's flow model of analysis, there are three concurrent flows which are data reduction, data display and conclusion drawing / verification.

4.3 Data Reduction

This is a process of selecting and transforming the data that appears in written transcripts (Huberman, 1994). Data reduction occurs throughout the initial and final stage of the project. That is it is an on going process that the researcher has started to do before going to the field. For instance, the researcher started by coming up with the broader topic of research (domestic workers) and ended up refining the topic to the challenges facing domestic workers. Thereafter, the researcher came up with among other issues written on domestic workers, literature that specifically addresses the research questions and objectives. The theoretic frame work of this study was established through selecting the theory used among other theories thus utilizing data reduction skill of the flow model. The data reduction method that has been adopted is a code sheet and this is where responses and emerging themes are recorded. This method allows the researcher to have a personal reflection column where she relates the findings to the theoretic frame work and the literature review.

4.4 Data display

This is an organised, compressed information that allows conclusions. This display, as the name suggest, involves assembling and organising information in a visual manner, for example, the use of graphs, matrices and charts. In this study, the researcher displayed the demographic information of domestic workers in terms of the gender, age range, level of education so as to draw conclusion on the common characteristics of domestic workers in general.

4.5 Conclusion drawing and verification

Hurberman and Miles (1994) state that the final conclusion may not appear until data collection is over. Therefore, the researcher found out the meaning of findings and verified the conclusion in relation to the similarities and differences that emerged as themes from the raw data.

4.6 ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Babbie (2004) indicate that everyone in the study, need to be aware of the general agreements shared by the researcher concerning the considerations to be made in conducting the study. It is the duty of the researcher to me sure that the respondents are engaged in the study. Therefore, the researcher had to make the respondents feel free by assuring them that their contribution is valuable and that their names and identities are not required. Respect and dignity of respondents will be observed. Their honest and genuine responses are of great assistance in the study. In case the respondent does not understand English, the researcher translated to Setswana. The researcher considered the following principles:

Participation: The participation of the respondents was voluntary and based on the informed consent of the respondents. The respondents' were not be forced to respond.

Confidentiality: The researcher assured the respondents confidentiality and that their names are not required.

Harm: The researcher caused no harm to the respondents by using their time consciously. There were no emotional harm that cropped up and if it happened otherwise the researcher could refer them to the relevant authorities with consent of participant.

4.7 LIMITATIONS OF STUDY

The following are likely to be encountered by the researcher:

The study targets domestic workers and it happened that some of them were not around by the time the data was collected data because of the Christmas holidays.

The researched identified more domestic workers to supplement the five (5) of them who went for the holidays.

Collecting data from domestic workers was problematic as some of them were not allowed to accept any visitors in the absence of the employers. In case of this kind, the researcher asked their employers to sign the consent letters so as to allow the domestic workers' participant in the study. However, some employers refused to sign consent letters hence the researcher moving to additional supplementary participants

Domestic workers employers refused to be interviewed because they felt that domestic worker issues were their personal matter hence not allowing anyone to know about their daily interactions with their employees. The researcher minimised this by assuring the respondents that the information they disclosed is kept confidential.

Some domestic workers (those who are expatriates with no permits) did not want to be interviewed as they thought that the researcher was under cover for Botswana Police. An assurance that the researcher was not undercover for any law force was made though some remained unconvinced and did not participated in the study.

One of the domestic workers did not freely participate as her employer insisted to listen to the responses. Therefore in that case, the issue of genuineness and honesty were threatened.

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Appendix

INTERVIEW GUIDE

INTRODUCTION

Hello, sir/madam. I am Reginah Mmisi-Nfila, a fourth year social work student at the University of Botswana. As part of my studies, I am carrying out a research project which focuses on investigating the challenges facing domestic workers in Phase 2. Its purpose is to describe the relationship between domestic workers and their employers, their working and living conditions, as well as identifying measures to improve the welfare of domestic workers.

Interview guide for domestic workers

1. DEMOGRAPHIC DATA

1.1 Age:

1.2 Gender:

1.3 Marital Status:

1.4 Location:

1.5 No of dependents:

1.6 Wage:

1.7 No of working hours per day:

1.8 Start time and knock off time:

1.9 Highest level of education:

2.0 WORKING CONDITIONS

2.1 What does your job entail? List all the major activities.

2.2 How many people live in the household you are working for?

2.3 Do you stay in your employer's yard? If yes or no, why?

2.4 Are there equipment and materials to use as a protective measure in carrying out your work activities?

2.5 Do you sometimes work overtime? If yes, what times?

2.6 Are you entitled to overtime payment?

2.7 If yes, how much and if no, what are the reasons?

2.8 Do you earn a leave or off days?

2.9 When do you normally go for leave or have off days?

3.0 Did you acquire training for your job?

3.0 LIVING CONDITIONS

3.1 Do you stay in your employer's yard?

3.2 If yes or no, explain why?

3.3 If yes, are you accommodated in the main house or servant's quarters? Explain the reasons why?

3.4 Do you have dependents or children?

3.5 If yes, how many of them?

3.6 How often do you check on your children?

3.7 Do you have someone who is helping you to support your dependents?

3.8 If you are not staying with your employer, are you staying in a rented accommodation?

3.9 If yes, how much do you pay?

4.0 How many rooms are there?

4.1 If you are staying with your employer is it for free or there is an amount that you pay?

4.2 If you are staying with your employer, are you cooking your food separately or you share with them?

4.3 If yes, give the reasons.

3. PROBLEMS FACING DOMESTIC WORKERS

3.1 What problems do you encounter in your work? List them.

3.2 What is the most challenging problems in your work?

3.3 What are your challenges pertaining to your work payment?

3.4 Do you afford paying for your accommodation? Explain.

3.5 Is the accommodation basic enough for you and your dependents? 3.6 What are the disadvantages of staying with your employer?

3.7 What are the disadvantages of staying away from your employer's yard?

3.8 Do you have problems associated with earning a leave or off days? Explain.

3.9 How did you establish your wage; did you negotiate it with your employer?

4.0 Is there a compensation allowance, in case you have an accident during work?

4.1 Did you sign a contract with your employer? If yes or no, why?

4.0 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN DOMESTIC WORKERS AND THEIR EMPLOYERS

4.1 What rights do you have?

4.2 Are they respected?

4.3 How do you describe your relationship with your employer?

4.4 Does your living arrangement have an impact on the way you relate with your employer?

4.5 If yes or no, explain.

4.6 Does your employer appreciate your work? Explain.

4.7 Does your employer praise your work? Explain.

4.8 Other than employer- worker relationship, do you have any form of relationship with your employer?

4.9 If yes, explain?

5.0 Do you have any problematic relationship with your employer?

5.1 If yes, what are those problems? Explain.

5.2 If you have problematic relationship with your employer, why do you continue maintaining the job?

5.0 MEASURES TO IMPROVE THE WELFARE OF DOMESTIC WORKERS

5.1 What is your monthly wage?

Below P200.

P201-P300

P301-P400

P401-P500

P501-P600

P600 and above

5.1 Are you able to meet your needs with your monthly wage? If no, why?

5.2 How much do you spend on the following;

Food

Transport

Accommodation

Other necessities for your dependents

5.3 How does domestic work impact your welfare?

5.4 What do you think can be done to improve your welfare?

5.5 Do you think working on a contract is best? Why?

5.6 Is domestic work training necessary and why?

5.7 Who do you think should be the sponsor of that training?

5.8 What do you think the government can do to improve the welfare of domestic workers?

5.9 If you do not have problems with your employer, what did you do to maintain such a working environment?

6.0 Generally, do you think domestic workers are abused? Explain.

6.1 If yes, why do you think some domestic workers continue to stay in abusive working conditions?

End of the interview. Thanks for your participation.

Interview guide for domestic workers' employers.

1.0 WORKING AND LIVING CONDITIONS

1.1 What does your employee job entail?

1.2 What is the working arrangement?

1.3 Are you staying with your employee in the same premises?

1.4 Does your employee sometimes work overtime?

1.5 If yes, when does your employee work overtime, and if no, why ?

1.6 Is there any payment for that overtime?

1.7 If yes or no, explain.

1.8 How do you pay your employee? (cash or in kind)

1.9 If in kind, explain.

2.0 If cash how much?

Below P200

P201-P300

P301-P400

P401-P500

P501-P600

Above P600

2.1 Is domestic work training important, and why?

2.2 If yes, who do you think should sponsor the training?

2.3 What should be the qualification for one to enrol for the training?

2.4 Do you have any protective clothes for your employee? (e.g oven gloves)

2.0 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN DOMESTIC WORKERS AND THEIR EMPLOYERS

2.1 Do you stay with your employee?

2.2 If yes, does your employer pay for that accommodation?

- 2.3 If yes, do you share food items with your employer?
- 2.4 If your employee is not staying with you, does transport have any negative implication on the job? Explain.
- 2.5 How would you describe your relationship with your employee?
- 2.6 Do you have any problems with your employee? Explain.
- 2.7 What is the most outstanding problem in your relationship with your employee? 2.8 Is your employee hard working? Explain.
- 2.9 How does your employee relate with the rest of your family?
- 3.0 Generally, do you think domestic workers have problematic relationships with their employers?
- 3.1 If yes or no explain.
- 3.2 Do you think domestic workers have affairs with their employers?
- 3.3 If yes, why do you think domestic workers indulge in sexual relations with their employers?
- 3.41) Do you think domestic workers are exploited?
- 3.5 If yes, explain why is it that domestic workers continue to stay in exploitative work relations?

3. PROBLEMS FACING DOMESTIC WORKERS?

- 3.1 What are the problems facing domestic workers? List them
- 3.2 What could be the outstanding challenge they have in their field? 3.3 What can be the reason for domestic workers' job termination?
- 3.4 What can be done to minimize the problems faced by domestic workers?

Interview guide for the key informants

1. MEASURES TO IMPROVE THE WELFARE OF DOMESTIC WORKERS

1.1 Is domestic work important?

1.2 Is domestic work categorised within the informal sector of employment in Botswana?

1.3 What measures can be taken to improve the welfare of domestic workers?

1.4 What is your comment on providing domestic with vocational training?

1.5 Are the rights of domestic workers protected?

1.6 Is there any statutory obligation on working hours and overtime?

1.7 How can financial allocation in the national development plans and national budget improve the welfare of domestic workers?

1.8 What can be done to minimize the problems that domestic workers face at their workplaces?

1.9 How can the use of written contract benefit domestic workers welfare?

2.0 Are there any problems facing domestic workers that could be legal, economic and social? Explain each.

2.1 How can these situations of domestic workers be improved?